

The Role of Technology as a Key Driver to SMEs Competitiveness – A Case of SMEs in Nairobi County

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Abstract:

For decades now, Information Technology has helped deliver or facilitate several business benefits, including improved decision-making, flexibility, and productivity; internal operations efficiency; enhanced information management; lower cost business transactions; improved supply chain management and greater interconnections with business partners. However, it is the rapid pace and evolution of technological advances witnessed in more recent years that have helped "level the playing field" for SMEs. Such advances have resulted in unprecedented business opportunities. These advances in IT have resulted in the development of business models that are fundamentally different – traditional brick-and-mortar industries are being dominated, or completely replaced, by models that are essentially software-based, and physical boundaries are disappearing with more and more business data being transmitted and shared over the Internet. SME importance in a knowledge-based economy has been highly appreciated and acknowledged. Moreover, in the present economy, Micro and Small Enterprises are facing tremendous challenges and threats to survive in a competitive environment Information, and Communications Technology in the recent past has brought both challenges and opportunities to Small and Medium Sized organizations. The study seeks to analyze the role of Technology as a key driver for SMEs growth in Kenya. The researcher will use cross-sectional survey. The target population is 200 Small and Medium Enterprises in Nairobi County with a specific focus on SMEs in the central business district. Descriptive statistics will be used, and data were collected using both closed and open-ended questionnaires. The findings of this established that Technology plays a key role in creating competitiveness in SMEs which have strongly embraced and recommends that the Kenya Government should encourage the use of Technology in all their operations. This study identified Technology as a critical driver of the Vision 2030, a sustainable goal of economic transformation

Key Words: *Technology, Small and Medium Enterprises, Nairobi County and Information Communications Technology*

Introduction

Across the African continent, policies, programs, projects and plans are formulated to improve lives of citizens-empowering the people, which are the core aims of development. Sadly, most of these policies, programs, projects, and plans formulated are for short-term purposes and are not totally implemented. Furthermore, they do not highlight all aspects of development which includes technology, education, agriculture, health among others. Consequently, it becomes hard for African countries to get to a stage where they can be referred to as developed countries. African countries can only be developed if and only if they work towards sustainable development through embracing technology in the management of its SMEs. Thiam (2009) indicates that sustainable development is a global crusade movement, which is a process rather than an end goal. Green (2011) noted that this process requires constant analysis and evaluation of the emerging trends in the discussion so as to take the issue of technology and sustainable development to the next level. Sustainable development is the process of ensuring that the present development is maintained and sustained for the present and future. It focuses on building the nation for the future in order to improve the lives of its citizens. To sustain and achieve sustainable development, reliable, potential and revolutionary efficient tools must be employed. These technological tools are the ICTs such as the mobile phones, microcomputers, e-mail, Internet among others. It is with this background a study to investigate the role of Technology as a Key driver to SMEs competitiveness a case of SMEs in Nairobi County. Limited access to markets remains a severe constraint to SME growth and competitiveness in Kenya owing to a shrinking domestic market due to globalization. (GOK, 2005; KIPPRA, 2006). Limited access to market information makes SMEs less aware of opportunities in the market. Overall aggregate demand for the sector's products is low, and markets are saturated due to overproduction and dumping of cheap imports. Markets do not function well due to insufficient information, high transaction costs and stiff competition for similar products. High transaction costs are due to market inefficiencies and information asymmetry. SMEs face difficulties accessing markets due to limited market information, poor marketing capacity and poor market research leading to a discrepancy between the supply and demand. (KIPPRA, 2006).

The study was guided by the following objectives:

- To determine perceptions of employees and management of SMEs towards adoption and use of technology.
- To examine factors hindering SMEs in adoption and use of technology.
- To establish how the use of Technology has contributed to SMEs competitiveness.

Literature Review

It is widely accepted that SMEs are the backbone of modern market economies, thus play an important role particularly in developing countries. In most countries, SMEs are the dominant form of business organizations, accounting for over 90% of the business population, and they play a key role in driving sustainable economic growth and job creation. Bringing SMEs up to speed with the digital revolution is not just a matter of improving their quarterly profits, but also about creating growth and jobs. In the digital age, no business can thrive without the better use of ICT. Kozak, (2011) emphasized that SMEs grow two to three times faster when they embrace

Definition of SMEs

Internationally, it is the only European Union that have taken some steps in adopting a commonly accepted definition of SMEs, though there are still debate among countries in the block. Way back in 2003, the commission of European Union adopted a definition of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises, which provides a framework for defining SMEs as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Definition of micro, small and medium-sized enterprises by European Commission
Enterprise Type Sheet No. of Employees Turnover Balance

Micro	< 10	≤€ 2 million	≤€ 2 Million
Small	< 50	≤€10 million	≤€10 million
Medium-sized	<250	≤€ 50 million	≤€ 43 million

In simple terms, European Commission defined SMEs as enterprises with less than 250 workers. With respect to fiscal criteria, finances cannot exceed € 50 million as a turnover, and/or €43 million on a balance sheet. In addition, the Commission of European Communities specifies terms of ownership, reporting that SMEs ought to be independent, with less than 25% of it being owned by outside interest (Kozak, 2011). Due to different definitions of SMEs, it is important to develop a working definition that can effectively support technological needs or the purpose of the given task. This paper adopted a definition as per the European Commission

Technology use by Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs)

Most studies on technology adoption and use comprise a considerable area of research within the ICT domain (Green, 2011), there continues to be a need for enhanced understanding of the role of technology as a driver of SMEs competitiveness. Barua, (2011) argues that lack of technology environment including lack of critical mass use, unavailability of ideal technology, e-business infrastructure are major external hindrances obstructing technology adoption and use by SMEs. Kirby & Turner, (2012) observe that majority of external hindrances come from business related barriers. Ritchie and Brindley (2010) noted that there are three barriers to adoption and use of technology by SMEs. These are external pressures (requirements by trading partners and competitiveness from other players), organizational readiness and perceived benefits of the technology. The authors argue that perceived benefits from a key reason why many SMEs adopts and continues to use the technology. According to Muraya (2009), external environment (suppliers, buyers, government interventions and competitive pressure) are very crucial factors influencing the use of technology by many SMEs. The author suggests that environmental and organizational characteristics are required for proper implementation of technologies in SMEs businesses. Alila and Ove (2011) observed that, as a primary external factor of the technology adoption and use, government role is a very important factor in the integration of the technology by SMEs. Most of the government roles, the author notes, are related to financial supports including direct support of the development of the application, tax breaks on technology infrastructure, etc. In a study performed by Thong and Yap (2011), (2010) in Malaysia found that perceived benefits, government support, and management support are important predictors that influenced SMEs to adopt and use technology. In another study, Paul and Pascale (2013), (2011) in Brunei identified factors influencing adoption and use of technology by SMEs as perception of relative advantage, CEOs perception, CEOs characteristics, complexity, compatibility and organizational size. A study carried out by Sakai (2012) in Taiwan SMEs found that technical backing and computing skills were strong anchors of the perception of usefulness and exercise direct influence on adoption and use of the technology. Further study by Thong and Yap (2011), (2013) found that adoption and use of advanced technology were significantly related to innovativeness and advocated that innovativeness as a significant trait in determining technology adoption and use among SMEs in Taiwan. The ability of SMEs to survive in an increasingly competitive global environment is largely dependent upon their capacity to leverage information as a resource and to benefit from the value of information. SMEs need ready access to comprehensive, relevant information since they operate in severe time and capacity constraints. They require information on business trends and markets; business environment, legal and regulatory aspects, business management, customer needs, business expansion, and diversification; technology; business opportunities; linkages and business partnerships. (Schleberger, 1998) Limited access to opportune, current, relevant and adequate information is a notable constraint to SMEs in Kenya. The enterprises struggle to gain access to important information needed for improved productivity, customer satisfaction, improved cycle time and opportunities at the marketplace. (ITG, 2002 in Hanna, 2010) Market signals on business opportunities and customer trends are not communicated effectively to SMEs, who perform better in information-rich environments (KIPPRA, 2006).

Conceptual Framework

The current study focused on a conceptual framework essential in identifying factors influencing SMEs in adoption and use of technology in their businesses. The framework identifies the problem as lack of effective adoption and use of technology by SMEs due to challenges of cost, unreliable electricity supply, inadequate infrastructure, poor maintenance of technological infrastructures, government policies, negative attitude towards technology and lack of technical know-how on technological instruments. Remedies are identified as establishing proper policies, expanding connections of electricity, exploring alternative sources of power and training of employees. Impacts are identified as improved business performance, improved communications, increased profit margins, increase innovations and increased areas of technology applications.

Fig. 1 conceptual framework

Research Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design where responses and perception held by the respondents were studied. Descriptive survey research is used to investigate populations by selecting samples to discover and analyze occurrences at a particular point in time. Orodho (2008) argue that this form of research design provides quantitative descriptions of some part of the population. This study was carried out among SMEs operating in Nairobi County. The study involved 50 managers, 50 SMEs owners, and 100 workers of SMEs found within the City County. Stratified sampling technique was used to ensure that the different sub-groups of SMEs were proportionally represented and their characteristics were accounted for. The study used structured questionnaires for collecting data, which were designed to capture participants’ perception and knowledge technology plays in creating or enhancing SMEs in Nairobi City County. According to Koul (2012), questionnaires are used to offer a considerable advantage in administration and present a better stimulus for a larger number of populations simultaneously and provide researchers with an easy way of gathering data.

Findings and Discussions

In this section, discussions, and findings of this research are presented in tables according to specific themes of study. Also, references to pertinent studies in the literature and discussions of data collected are provided.

Demographics of Participants in This Study

On the gender of respondents, data collected showed that majority 125 (62.5%) were males while females were 75 (37.5%). These findings indicated that most of SMEs workers in Nairobi County were dominated by males. The data on age shows that majority of respondents were between 31-40 years, 83 (41.5%), followed by 41-50 years at 52 (26.0%), over 50 years were 38 (19%) and less than 30 years were 27 (13.5%). This data revealed most of the age groups were represented in this study. As shown in table 3, most of the participants had attained primary education.

Table 2. Demographics of participants in the study

Variable Category	No.	%
Gender Males	125	62.5
Females	75	37.5
Age Less than 30	27	14
31-40	83	41
41-50	52	26
Over 50	38	19
Level of education		
Primary	47	23
Secondary	69	35
University	84	42

Respondents' Perception of the Use of Technology by SMEs

In order to assess the perceptions of respondents towards adoption and use of technology by SMEs, a five-point Likert-type scale with 15 items ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree) was constructed. The respondents were asked to indicate their perception by circling the appropriate answer. The percentages and means of responses were then calculated as shown in table 4.

Table 4. Descriptive Statistics of respondents' perceptions of the use of technology by SMEs

Variable	SD(%)	D(%)	N(%)	A(%)	SA(%)	Mean	St.d
Improve productivity	2.63	3.16	14.72	58.07	21.42	4.34	0.87
Improve customer satisfaction	5.72	11.53	17.32	34.57	30.86	3.78	0.92
Keep up with competitors	4.78	6.92	21.63	36.34	30.33	4.17	0.84
Improve working on joint projects with others	7.23	15.34	36.72	31.61	9.01	3.42	0.97
Improves communication with suppliers	8.92	9.23	32.71	27.43	21.71	3.27	0.89
Increase operational efficiency	3.68	7.26	15.98	46.72	26.36	4.47	0.82
Increase staff satisfaction	11.82	13.67	17.21	29.73	27.57	3.67	0.91
Creates jobs	1.76	6.86	11.75	21.76	57.87	4.76	0.99
Working with technology is enjoyable	13.89	17.34	36.65	19.72	12.40	2.89	0.78
Puts more works on shoulders of staff	35.62	29.56	17.48	10.16	7.18	1.32	0.67
Technological tools are difficult to use	27.89	41.87	16.76	7.82	5.66	2.13	0.82
Technology relieves staff from daily work	38.23	31.65	11.78	11.21	7.13	1.41	0.69
Knowledge of how to use technology is difficulty	21.47	36.74	14.63	12.36	14.80	2.31	0.86
Use of technology is a waste of time	48.56	31.98	12.72	3.57	3.17	1.07	0.62
Use of technology affects personal treatment of customers	29.37	31.25	21.21	11.63	6.54	2.17	0.79

Note. SD = strongly disagree; D = disagree; N = no opinion; A = agree; SA = strongly agree.

As shown in table 4, the mean of responses in the suggestion that adoption and use of technology will improve the productivity of SMEs was 4.34 (St.D = 0.87) which tended to 4, meaning that majority of respondents' agreed adoption and use of technology by SMEs will improve their productivity. On the suggestion that technology will improve customer satisfaction, the mean of responses was 3.78 (St.D = 0.92) which was approximately 4 meaning that respondents agreed that implementation of technology by SMEs in their business would improve customer satisfaction. The majority of respondents also agreed that technology could help keep up with competition (Mean of responses 4.17, St.D = 0.84), working with technology can increase operational efficiency (mean of responses 4.47, St.D = 1.82) and increase staff satisfaction (mean of responses 3.67, St.d = 0.91). An overwhelming majority of respondents strongly agreed that technology could create jobs, with a mean of 4.76 (St.D = 0.99) which was approximately 5. These findings were consistency with the finding of a study done by Mingaine, (2013) that concluded adoption and use of technology improved management of SMEs as well enhancing their performance. With the suggestion that working with technology is enjoyable (mean of responses 2.89, St.D = 0.78), improve working on joint projects with other sectors (mean of responses 3.42, St.D = 0.97) and improves communication with suppliers (mean of responses 3.27, St.D = 0.89), all which tended towards 3, this meant that respondents had no idea that working with technology was enjoyable, improves joint ventures or improved communication with suppliers. These findings were attributed to the fact that most of SMEs in Nairobi County had not fully embraced the use of technology; hence they did not have views of its importance.

On the suggestion that technology puts more works on shoulders of staff (mean of responses 1.32, St.d = 0.67), relieves staff from daily work (mean of responses 1.41, St.D = 0.69) and working with technology is a waste of time (mean of responses 1.07, St.D = 0.62). All these responses were approximately 1, meaning that respondents strongly disagreed that technology puts more works on shoulders of staff, relieves staff from daily work and working with technology was a waste of time. The findings are in agreement with Onyango et al., (2014) who found in a study of SMEs in Kenya, that use of technological tools helped CEO and staffs of SMEs execute their duties effectively, and they used them for enhancing business performance.

Conclusion

Technology holds a lot of potential for enhancing market access and yet use by SMEs is limited as compared to larger enterprises. The use of ICT for marketing by SMEs still remains low despite SMEs having access to these tools. Majority of SMEs use ICT for communication, social networking, and general information acquisition. There seems to be lack of awareness of the range of opportunities that ICT offers for increased market competitiveness. Limited use of ICT for marketing can also be attributed to perceived high costs of appropriate applications, security issues and limited knowledge and skills on some ICT applications, e.g., e-commerce. The study recommends enhanced the use of Technology to create a strong, sustainable competitive advantage.

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